

Responding to the challenge of quality education: Customer service satisfaction analysis in AY 2014-2018

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Abstract

This study evaluates the services provided by St. Dominic College of Asia for the past four years from AY 2014-2015 to AY 2017-2018 using a customer satisfaction survey. Utilizing the descriptive, longitudinal research design particularly the trend analysis, all students of the higher education were asked to answer a customer satisfaction survey questionnaire that has been used for over five years. The results revealed that almost all offices, facilities and general services follow a downward trend since 2014-2015 but tends to peak up in AY 2017-2018. Moreover, it also shows that with the exception of offices, facilities and general services did not meet the institutional set standard of 3.9/5 for the customer satisfaction rating. The study also suggests the lack of consistency of making the satisfaction rating consistently higher than 3.9 as their instances that the rating is high in the first semester but plunges in the second semester. Therefore, consistent monitoring of operations and services should be done to prevent this scenario to happen for the next years to come, particularly during second semester.

Keywords: Quality education. Customer satisfaction. Customer service. Operations. Longitudinal analysis.

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Introduction

As Bonstingl (2001) put it, quality is a way of being. It is a lifetime spiritual, physical, and mental journey that permeates all aspects of one's life. Quality emerges from the depths of our hearts and souls. Then it develops in our interpersonal relationships. Quality naturally thrives in and characterizes our families and other organizations to which we belong whenever it becomes the essence of our existence when we are alone and when we are with others. Quality becomes the essence of our schools, workplaces, and communities, then our society, and eventually the global village of which we are a part.

However, quality education is not only claimed but it should be felt by the customers of this noble industry—the students. As it becomes part of every institution's body, soul, and spirit, it should be more tangibly experienced by the customers since according to Johnston et al. (2020), customers are the last judge of whether a service's quality meets expectations, and their continuous support determines the service's long-term viability. Despite the fact that the obligation to satisfy customers should "go without saying," many businesses struggle to do so.

Customers are assumed to desire certain things, and even if they have been consulted, it may have been so long ago that the knowledge is at best obsolete and at worst highly dangerous. Professional services, in particular, are typically afflicted by the belief that they know everything since they are the experts (Johnston and Clark, 2008). Understanding what satisfies and delights customers is a constant challenge that must be addressed through a variety of methods to guarantee that the responses do not fall into well-established patterns for a variety of reasons. This is what this study purports to achieve.

Importance of Customer Satisfaction

Kierczak (2018) suggested five reasons why customer satisfaction is essential. First and foremost, a loyal consumer is a valuable asset that should be guarded and hidden from the public eye. According to the White House Office of Consumer Affairs, loyal clients are worth up to ten times what they paid for their first product. Getting a new customer is more expensive than keeping an existing one. The second reason is that customers can leave a company's client list in an instant.

The third reason is that it all comes down to money. It should come as no surprise that a company's income is affected by customer satisfaction. The essential metrics—such as number of mentions and repeated transactions, as well as customer lifetime value and churn—can be influenced both positively and negatively by the customer's opinion and feelings about the brand. Customers who are satisfied will not consider competing offers; instead, they will gladly interact with the group again, make a purchase, and spread the word about the product.

Fourth, client satisfaction is an important aspect in standing out from the crowd. Kate Zabriskie, as quoted by Okeke (2016), said that “although your customers won’t love you if you give bad service, your competitors will.” Lastly, a positive customer experience can elevate a brand. The importance of customer satisfaction should not be neglected, particularly in the planning of marketing and positioning campaigns.

Customers’ Perceptions, Expectations, and Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction can be influenced to some degree by changing customers' views and expectations of service delivery. Simply put, customer satisfaction is defined as a customer's evaluation of a service based on a comparison of their perceptions of service delivery to their prior expectations (Bitner & Hubbert, 1994). Customers should be satisfied if their perceptions of the service, the experience, and the results match their expectations. They will be more than satisfied, if not delighted, if their perception of the service exceeds their expectations. They may be disappointed, even disgusted or angered, if their impressions of the service do not fulfill their expectations (Oliver & DeSarbo, 1988).

Hence, satisfaction is the result of the consumer’s evaluation of a service, which is sometimes referred to as perceived service quality and can be shown on a collection from delight to extreme satisfaction, which is in this study labelled 1 to 5.

Therefore, this study sought to evaluate the satisfaction level of students on the services offered by St. Dominic College of Asia (SDCA) and determine the trend from Academic Years 2014 to 2018, if indeed SDCA has been improving, maintaining, or deteriorating in its services. Further, it also determines if SDCA has met the standards it set in its services as perceived and experienced by the student-customers.

Methodology

The descriptive, longitudinal design (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018), specifically trend analysis was used in this research which utilized the results from AY 2014-2015 to 2017-2018 using an institutional survey questionnaire on customer satisfaction which is in the form of Likert-scale with 1 as the lowest and 5 as the highest. With the Department of Student Affairs and Services (DSAS) spearheading this study, the questionnaires were floated to students across all departments. This went for the population of SDCA higher education students with an acceptable retrieval rate of 70%. The DSAS facilitated the gathering and initial tally of data which was endorsed to the Research and Development Office (RDO) for statistical treatment and analysis.

Results and Discussion

On the Customer Satisfaction of the Services of Various Offices

Table 1 shows the summary of the weighted mean of the rating for each office that has direct transactions with the students. These offices are more frequently used by students/customers in all their transactions with the school, from enrolment, payments, retrieval and submission of credentials, health issues and problems, guidance and counselling including discipline, co and extracurricular activities, food and transportation services and others.

Moreover, to show the trend, line graphs below follow this tabular presentation.

Table 1. Customer satisfaction from AY 2014-2018 (Offices)

Offices	2014-2015		2015-2016		2016-2017		2017-2018		Average
	1st	2nd	1st	2nd	1st	2nd	1st	2nd	
Admission	4.32	4.31	4.31	4.19	4.02	3.96	4.18	3.99	4.16
Health	4.12	4.34	4.34	4.06	3.98	3.90	4.14	3.88	4.10
Student Services	4.12	4.40	4.40	4.16	4.07	4.10	4.22	3.98	4.18
Student Wellness	4.25	4.29	4.29	4.08	3.97	4.01	4.15	3.92	4.12
Registrar	3.88	4.06	4.06	3.92	3.86	3.91	3.86	3.79	3.92
Accounting	3.66	4.10	4.10	3.95	3.97	3.94	4.04	3.89	3.96
DLRC	3.95	4.20	4.20	4.10	4.08	3.83	4.13	3.91	4.05
Cafe Bariga	3.87	4.18	4.18	3.97	3.90	3.97	3.75	3.73	3.94
Tea Ysabelle	3.80	4.13	4.13	3.94	3.74	3.81	3.68	3.70	3.87
Cafe Alfresco	3.97	4.17	4.17	4.04	3.92	3.91	3.81	3.72	3.96
Business Center	3.55	4.05	4.05	4.00	3.83	3.54	3.98	3.81	3.85
MIS	3.87	4.01	4.01	3.87	3.74	4.03	4.08	3.82	3.93
Motor Pool	3.58	3.94	3.94	3.79	3.65	3.81	3.83	3.75	3.79

Table 1 shows the various offices of SDCA with the summary of their mean ratings in the customer satisfaction survey conducted by the DSAS and RDO for the academic years 2014-2015 to 2017-2018. Comparing the results according to offices, it can be gleaned that the admission (4.16), health services (4.10), student affairs and services (4.18), student wellness offices (4.12) and the Dominican Learning Resource Center (DLRC) [4.05] have been performing higher than other offices for the past four years. However, offices such as the motor pool (3.79), business center (3.85), and Tea Ysabelle (3.87) performed less than the rest.

Looking at the trend according to the academic years from 2014 to 2018, it can be suggested based on the results that despite high points, there is a downward trend in the customers’ satisfaction. The graphs below are the specifics of this observation and the corresponding trend analysis.

Figure 1. Trend analysis of SDCA customer’s satisfaction from AY 2014-2018 (Offices) [part 1]

It can be gleaned in Figure 1 that the admission office's performance plunged from 4.32 in 2014-2015 to 3.99 in the second semester of 2017-2018. However, it seems that the said office regained in the first semester of 2017-2018 for 4.18 from a lower 3.96, yet it ended up at 3.99, which is still a good score. A similar predicament happens with the health services and the student services offices with the exception of the registrar which has a consistent downward trend from 2015 to the second semester of 2017-2018.

Figure 2. Trend analysis of SDCA customer's satisfaction from AY 2014-2018 (Offices) [part 2]

In this second set, as shown in Figure 2 above, the Accounting Office and the Dominican Learning Resource Center (DLRC) also experience the same trend with the admissions office. However, the two canteens, Cafe Alfresco and Cafe Bariga have a trend with that of the Registrar, which have been consistently going down, however, the third canteen, Tea Ysabelle, is inconsistent in its rating of ups and downs.

Figure 3. Trend analysis of SDCA customer's satisfaction from AY 2014-2018 (Offices) [part 3]

Furthermore, Figure 3 shows that the business center has a downward trend from AY 2015 to AY 2016-2017 but it peaks up in the first semester of AY 2017-2018. On the other hand, the Offices of Management Information System (MIS) and the Motor Pool have the same trend which is downward from 2014-2015 up to the first semester of 2016-2017 but peaked up in the second semester of 2016-2017.

On the Customer Satisfaction of SDCA's Facilities

Table 2. Customer satisfaction from AY 2014-2018 (Facilities)

Facilities	2014-2015		2015-2016		2016-2017		2017-2018		Average
	1st	2nd	1st	2nd	1st	2nd	1st	2nd	
Comfort Rooms	3.29	3.46	3.46	3.28	2.95	3.52	3.34	3.64	3.37
Gate Lobby	3.74	3.96	3.96	3.65	3.20	3.74	3.58	3.67	3.69
Hallways and benches	3.88	4.08	4.08	3.81	3.37	3.50	3.36	3.58	3.71
Gymnasium	3.49	3.86	3.86	3.60	3.00	3.49	3.43	3.56	3.54
Quadrangle	3.59	4.05	4.05	3.65	3.23	3.31	3.37	3.53	3.60

Table 2 summarizes the results of the customer satisfaction survey of SDCA's facilities. Among the facilities, hallways and benches get the highest rating of 3.71 but the comfort rooms get the lowest at 3.37; although some facilities got good ratings: Gate Lobby (3.69), Gymnasium (3.54), and Quadrangle (3.60). These ratings are good enough considering that the highest possible rating is 5; however, they all missed the standard set at 3.9.

Looking at how each facility has been rated for the past four years, Figure 4 shows the trend of rates given by student customers.

Figure 4. Trend analysis of customer satisfaction of the facilities

For the past four academic years, facilities have been rated below the set standard satisfaction rate of 3.9/5 yet the rating ranges from as low as 2.95 in AY 2016-2017 for the comfort rooms and as high as 4.08 for hallways and benches in AY 2014-2015. However, looking closely at the set trend, it has a downward trend from 2014-2015 to first semester of 2016-2017 but peaked up in the second semester of 2017-2018. Still, it never surpassed the high scores in 2014-2015.

On the Customer Satisfaction of SDCA General Services

Table 3. Customer satisfaction from AY 2014-2018 (General services)

General Services	2014-2015		2015-2016		2016-2017		2017-2018		Average
	1st	2nd	1st	2nd	1st	2nd	1st	2nd	
Cleanliness	3.78	3.87	3.87	3.64	3.49	3.72	3.66	3.71	3.78
Promptness of services	3.73	3.93	3.93	3.75	3.59	3.79	3.79	3.72	3.73
Courtesy of employees	3.87	4.02	4.02	3.86	3.74	3.75	3.87	3.79	3.87

Table 3 exemplifies a need of improvement in the area of general services such as cleanliness, promptness of services, and courtesy of employees as all of them missed the marked set at 3.9 for the past four years; although, they are still very good scores. Courtesy of employees topped with an average of 3.87 and cleanliness got a score of 3.71; while promptness of services at 3.73.

Figure 5. Trend analysis of customer satisfaction (General services)

Meanwhile, nothing has changed with the trend set as the general services also traversed the same path with the others. It also has a downward trend from 2014-2015 to first semester of 2016-2017 yet peaked from second semester of 2016-2017; although it never reached the highest ratings in 2014-2015.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Offices, facilities, and general services generally have not been maintaining their customer satisfaction ratings from 2014-2018. Hence, the trend is downward. However, for the latest academic year, the ratings, particularly in offices are peaking up. It is recommended that there is a need to strengthen services by close monitoring of leaders and managers' performance.

First semesters are generally 'fat month' as to customer satisfaction, but second semesters are considered lean months as ratings are plunging. This suggests that SDCA lacks the necessary consistency in maintaining its quality services. Thus, it is recommended that leaders should closely monitor operation services particularly in the second semester in which people might have so much familiarity and laxity in their services.

Facilities and general services are not meeting the SDCA-set standard. Therefore, it is recommended that the DASS should look into this more closely and find ways on how to meet the set standard of 3.9. This may also include the offices of the Motor Pool, Business Center, and Tea Ysabelle.

Continuous training of administrative support staff is essential to improve the student educational experience. The staff should help students to create a trusting relationship that enables to promote a caring community within and outside the institution. It is noted that there should have an initiative to consider their training and development needs and to discuss appropriate opportunities that would help shape them as "role models".

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